

Early alterations in the cognitive connectome precedes Mild Cognitive Impairment

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Focusing on topographic statistic dependencies, the cognitive connectome framework provides a more sensitive detection of cognitive alterations. This study examines connectome patterns in predementia stages.

METHODS: A neuropsychological battery measured cognitively healthy older adults (N = 822) at two timepoints, comparing stable controls with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) converts (n = 617; n = 116). Networks were estimated as regularized Gaussian graphical models (EBICglasso, 20 nodes, 190 edges), followed by Frobenius distance with permutations for global differences.

RESULTS: Significant differences between groups emerged at T0 (50/190 nodes, $p < .005$), and increasing at T1 (78/190, $p < .005$). Differences were predominantly intermodular (68% baseline; 76% longitudinal), involving phonological/semantic fluency, episodic memory, processing speed, and working memory.

DISCUSSION: MCI conversion is preceded by architectural cognitive reorganization and altered cross-domain integration. The cognitive connectome provides a complementary early-detection tool for individual at risk for MCI in preclinical stages.

Keywords: Aging, Cognition, Cognitive Connectome, Dementia, Mild Cognitive Impairment, Preclinical stages

1. Introduction

The detection of predementia clinical symptoms using neuropsychological measurements has been a topic of high interest in recent years ^{1, 2}. Due to the progressive nature of neurodegenerative diseases, initial stages of decline might remain undetected, not meeting the threshold for dementia. While biomarkers analysis can potentially detect the decline during the predementia stage, such analysis is costly and not widely accessible to the large public. Conversely, neuropsychological tests are non-invasive and can be easily conducted with limited resources. Notwithstanding, neuropsychological tests measure specific cognitive domains, thus requiring a clinical decline, albeit not severe enough to meet dementia criteria. Therefore, the transitional symptomatic stage of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI)^{1, 2} has become the main point of interest, identifying whether the processes leading to a conversion from healthy aging to dementia are detectable before objective clinical thresholds are crossed ^{1, 3}.

Nonetheless, it is suggested that the univariate design of most conventional neuropsychological tests limits the scope to scores on specific cognitive domains. While conventional univariate is well suited to identifying intergroup test or domain differences, the cognitive partition into separable outcomes makes them less capable of determining whether the pattern of interdependence among cognitive processes itself has changed ^{4, 5}. Conversely, shifting to the network-level framework of the cognitive connectome provides a different perspective. This framework conceptualizes cognition as a relational system, with its structure defined by the pattern of interconnections among functions, domains, and subtests ^{5, 6}, accounting for topological organization of statistical dependencies among

cognitive measures, representing neuropsychological variables as nodes and their conditional associations as edges^{4, 5, 7}. Its primary advantage is preserving the system's architecture: network-based representations retain information about the clustering, connections, and broader configurations of organized interdependent cognitive information^{4, 5, 7}. Framing cognition in this way is particularly relevant in aging and neurodegenerative research, where clinically meaningful change may involve reorganization of the relational architecture^{4, 5, 6}.

Notwithstanding, there is still limited evidence on whether the cognitive connectome is abnormal in individuals with Normal Cognition (NG) but later convert to MCI^{4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11}. Previous studies have reported alterations in relational patterns in prodementia stages of Lewy Body Dementia as well as Alzheimer's Disease^{8, 9, 12}. This is theoretically significant because the central question is whether system-level reorganization precedes the diagnostic threshold, constituting part of the preclinical trajectory^{1, 2, 5}. Moreover, prognostic research has largely concentrated on isolated neuropsychological MCI-dementia progression predictors, rather than investigating whether future conversion involves distributed reconfiguration of inter-test cognitive dependencies^{13, 14}. A further unresolved issue is within-person change across the conversion itself: whether the connectome differs before conversion and also undergoes reorganization as NG individuals develop clinically detectable MCI^{1, 5, 9}. Thus, the gap is twofold: whether future converters already show an atypical connectome while cognitively normal, and how that connectome changes across the conversion interval—questions that define the present study's originality^{5, 8, 9}.

This study aims to determine whether the cognitive connectome is altered before MCI emergence and whether it undergoes further reorganization across the

transition from normal cognition to clinically detectable impairment, addressing the two unresolved questions within a single network-based framework^{1, 5}. The first objective is to compare, at baseline, the connectome of NG individuals with that of baseline NG participants who later convert to MCI, to test whether future converters exhibit distinct relational organization within conventional diagnostic limits^{1, 2, 5}. The second objective is to examine whether the connectome changes within the converter group between baseline and follow-up, evaluating whether conversion is accompanied by additional reorganization of conditional dependencies^{7, 15}. We hypothesize that future converters will exhibit a distinct connectome at baseline relative to NG controls, reflecting a preclinical network-level signal^{5, 8, 11}. We further hypothesize that conversion will be associated with additional connectome reorganization within converters, distributed across the network and likely involving intermodular alterations rather than disruption confined to a single domain^{5, 6, 9}. These objectives and hypotheses position the study as an attempt to characterize whether impending MCI is foreshadowed by altered cognitive architecture and whether that architecture is further reshaped during conversion^{1, 2, 15}.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Design

Network analysis is uniquely suited to test whether future conversion is associated both with lower cognitive performance, as well as with a different organization of conditional dependencies among cognitive measures before and during the transition to MCI^{5, 7}. Modeling cognitive variables as nodes in regularized Gaussian graphical models is appropriate because these models estimate partial associations conditioned on all other variables, providing a system-level

representation of cognitive organization that aligns closely with the cognitive connectome construct, unlike analyses based solely on isolated scores or zero-order correlations^{5,7}. This design combines two complementary contrasts: first, whether baseline cognitively normal individuals who later convert to MCI already exhibit a different connectome than stable non-converters; second, whether the connectome undergoes further reorganization within converters between baseline and follow-up when conversion becomes manifest. This dual approach allows separation of preclinical signals from network changes associated with conversion, rather than conflating baseline vulnerability with subsequent clinical expression⁵. Formal network-comparison procedures are also essential, because the question is whether structures differ at the global and edge-specific level under inferential control, not merely whether graphs look visually different^{7,15}. Estimating connectomes at both time points and examining whole-network and edge-wise differences provides a coherent framework to test whether impending MCI is preceded by distributed cognitive reorganization and whether such reorganization intensifies or changes during conversion^{5,15}.

2.2. Participants

The participants of this study comprised 822 cognitively healthy individuals aged 65 to 87 years at baseline, living at home, without relevant psychiatric, neurological or systemic disorders. All of them were part of two equivalent datasets from two previous funded projects namely *Elderly Relatives of Alzheimer's Disease (ERAD): Influence of Subjective Cognitive Decline and Factors associated with healthy and pathologically aging in a sample of elderly people over 90 in the city of Madrid (MADRID+90)*. The main goal of the two projects was to both improve the early

detection and prevention of MCI and dementia and to increase knowledge about the determinants of healthy aging.

2.3. Cognitive measures

Participants completed a standardized neuropsychological battery at baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1) covering global cognition, episodic memory, language, attention/working memory, processing speed, and visuoconstructive/visual memory abilities. Neuropsychologists with broad experience in cognitive aging and dementias were in charge of applying the neuropsychological testing battery following the standard test instructions. Cognitive variables were entered as network nodes using raw test scores obtained at each timepoint and subsequently preprocessed for network modelling as described in the Statistical analysis section.

Global cognitive status was assessed with the Mini-Mental State Examination ¹⁶ (MMSE), using the total score as the node variable. Verbal episodic memory was assessed with the Free and Cued Selective Reminding Test ^{17, 19} (FCSRT); four indices from FCSRT were used as nodes: free recall immediate, total recall immediate, free recall delayed, and total recall delayed. Visuoconstructive performance and visual memory were assessed with the Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure ^{19, 20} (ROCF); four ROCF indices were used: completion time for the copy condition, copy score, immediate recall, and delayed recall. Confrontation naming was assessed with the short 15-item version of the Boston Naming Test ²¹ (BNT-15), using the number of correct spontaneous responses as the node variable. Verbal fluency was assessed using both semantic and phonemic tasks; semantic fluency nodes were the number of correct words generated for the categories animals, fruits & vegetables, and kitchen tools within the standard 60 seconds time, meanwhile

phonemic fluency nodes were the number of correct words generated for each of three letters namely P, M, and R ²². Working memory capacity was assessed using Digit Span ²³, with separate forward and backward scores as nodes. Processing speed was indexed with the Digit Symbol task ²³, using the total correct score as the node variable. Finally, visuospatial/executive drawing skills were assessed with the Clock Drawing test ²⁴, using the total score as the node variable.

2.4. Procedure

After signing the informed consent, all participants underwent a detailed assessment protocol, which was usually completed within four hours with appropriate breaks. The full assessment included a clinical semi-structured interview and a neurological and neuropsychological examination.

The participants were followed for three years. Clinical diagnoses were always agreed upon in consensus discussions between neurologists and neuropsychologists. When available, MRIs were considered to exclude the presence of macroscopic lesions or significant vascular damage. Each participant was then independently diagnosed after each visit based on their age, gender, cognitive reserve, functional information, and cognitive scores. However, the diagnoses were not based on psychometrically stable thresholds values, but rather on clinical impressions. The NIA-AA's criteria were used to diagnose core MCI which included ¹: (i) self- or informant-reported cognitive complaints; (ii) objective evidence of impairment in one or more cognitive domains; (iii) preserved independence in functional abilities; and (iv) not demented. All participants were diagnosed as cognitively healthy at baseline.

2.5. Ethics approval

Ethical approval for the ERAD and MADRID+90 studies was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of the Hospital Universitario Clínico San Carlos (Madrid, Spain) and the Ethics Committee of the Carlos III Institute of Health (Madrid, Spain), respectively. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. The authors confirm that all procedures contributing to this work comply with the ethical standards of the relevant national and institutional committees on human experimentation and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments. All methods were performed in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All analyses were conducted in R (v4.2.1) on Windows 10 x64 (build 26200) using a complete-case approach (participants with missing values in any variables required for a given contrast were excluded). Key packages included bootnet (v1.6), igraph (v2.1.4), dplyr (v1.1.4), and readr (v2.1.5).

The analytic strategy comprised a baseline case–control contrast and a within-converter paired contrast across time. At baseline (T0), cases were incident MCI converters (n = 116), i.e., participants who were clinically classified as cognitively normal at T0 and subsequently met criteria for MCI during follow-up; controls (n = 617), were defined as stable non-converters with ≥ 3 years follow-up. For the paired analysis, we restricted to MCI converters with complete data at both T0 and T1 (n = 116) to test within-subject network reconfiguration accompanying the transition from T0 (cognitively normal) to T1 (MCI diagnosis).

Cognitive variables were treated as network nodes and analyzed at baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1). To ensure consistent directionality (higher scores indicating better performance), time-based measures (e.g., ROCF completion time) were sign-inverted prior to modeling. To reduce demographic confounding, each cognitive node was residualized using linear regression: at T0 we adjusted for age, gender, and education, and at T1 for age at follow-up, gender, and education. To avoid artefactual differences induced by condition-specific preprocessing, residualization and standardization were applied using pooled parameters within each analysis set. Specifically, for the T0 case–control comparison, regression models and z-scoring constants (mean/SD) were estimated on the pooled sample (converters + stable controls) and applied identically to both groups. For the paired converter analysis, T0 and T1 were residualized using their respective covariate sets and then jointly standardized using pooled mean/SD computed on the concatenated residual matrices, ensuring a shared scale across timepoints.

Networks were estimated as regularized Gaussian graphical models (GGMs) using EBICglasso (tuning = 0.5, threshold = TRUE, corMethod = "cor") yielding weighted undirected partial association networks. With 20 cognitive nodes, inference was performed over 190 unique undirected edges.

Whole-network differences between conditions were tested using the Frobenius distance between estimated EBICglasso weight matrices, $D = \|W_1 - W_0\|_F$. For the baseline case–control comparison (stable controls vs future converters at T0), significance was assessed via permutation with size-matching (randomly sampling $n_{\min} = 116$ controls per iteration to match the converter group) and recomputing D under shuffled group labels. For the within-converter

longitudinal comparison (T1 vs T0), significance was assessed using a paired-swap permutation (randomly swapping T0/T1 labels within individuals) and recomputing D . For both contrasts, we used 2000 permutations and computed one-sided permutation p-values with a +1 correction: $p = (1 + \#\{D_{\text{perm}} \geq D_{\text{obs}}\}) / (B + 1)$.

Edge-level inference followed a two-stage resampling framework: (i) construction of bootstrap edge-weight distributions by repeated network re-estimation, and (ii) permutation-based testing of edge-wise t statistics derived from those bootstrap distributions, with multiplicity controlled using Benjamini-Hochberg FDR (BH-FDR) across all 190 edges. Common parameters were 200 bootstrap network re-estimations per condition, bootstrap sub-sampling fraction 0.80 (thus $\text{sub_n} = \text{floor}(0.8 \times \text{n_case}) = 92$), and 2000 permutations for each edge-wise test. Analyses were parallelized (cores = 13).

2.6.1. Baseline group comparison (T0): stable controls vs converters

Within each group, bootstrap samples of size sub_n were drawn with replacement, an EBICglasso network was re-estimated for each resample, and the resulting edge weights were stored to form group-specific edge-weight distributions. For each edge, a descriptive effect estimate was computed as the difference in mean bootstrap edge weights (converter minus control). Statistical significance was assessed by computing an observed Welch-type t statistic comparing the two bootstrap distributions. The null distribution was generating by permuting case/control labels across bootstrap replicates (while preserving the number of replicates per group) and recomputing the edge-wise t statistic for each permutation. Two-sided p-values were computed with a +1 correction: $p =$

$$\frac{1 + \#\{|t_{\text{perm}}| \geq |t_{\text{obs}}|\}}{B_{\text{perm}} + 1}, \text{ followed by BH-FDR correction across edges (q-values).}$$

2.6.2. Longitudinal within-converter comparison (paired): T1 – T0

To preserve within-subject structure, bootstrap resamples were generated by sampling converters (size sub_n , with replacement) and re-estimating networks at T0 and T1 using the same resampled subject indices. For each bootstrap replicate, paired edge-wise change scores were computed as $\Delta w = w_{T1} - w_{T0}$, yielding a bootstrap distribution of paired edge changes for each edge. For each edge, an observed one-sample t statistic tested whether the mean Δw differed from zero. The null distribution was constructed via sign-flip permutations applied to bootstrap replicates (multiplying each replicate's Δw vector by +1 or -1 with probability 0.5), yielding two-sided p-values with the same +1 correction and BH-FDR correction across edges.

To summarize the localization of significant edge differences at the domain level, significant edges were mapped onto a fixed community structure derived from Louvain community detection applied to the absolute-weight adjacency matrix of the stable-control T0 network (reference). Significant edges were summarized as within-module vs between-module connections and by module-pair counts.

Edges were considered statistically significant at $q(\text{FDR}) < 0.05$. Given 2000 permutations, the minimum attainable p-value under the +1 correction is $1/(2000 + 1) \approx 0.0005$.

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

The baseline case-control analytic set comprised 617 stable controls (non-converters with ≥ 3 years follow-up) and 116 future converters (participants cognitively normal at baseline and defined by subsequent MCI conversion). The

within-converter longitudinal analytic set comprised 116 MCI converters with complete neuropsychological data at both baseline (T0) and follow-up (T1).

As summarized in Table 1, future MCI converters were older at baseline, whereas gender distribution did not differ and education was broadly comparable. Converters also showed lower raw cognitive performance across multiple domains at T0, and within converters, decline from T0 to T1 was evident for most cognitive tests.

3.2. Whole-network differences (global network contrast)

Whole-network differences were tested by comparing EBICglasso weight matrices using the Frobenius distance and permutation-based inference (Figure 1).

At baseline (T0), the whole-network difference between stable controls and future converters was significant (observed Frobenius distance $D_{\text{obs}} = 1.09048$; one-sided permutation $p = 0.00499$; 2000 permutations; size-matched with $n_{\text{min}} = 116$). The observed distance exceeded the 99th percentile of the null distribution ($q_{0.99} = 1.06066$). Within converters, the whole-network change from T0 to T1 was also significant under a paired-swap permutation scheme ($D_{\text{obs}} = 1.24203$; one-sided $p = 0.00199$; 2000 permutations). Again, the observed distance exceeded the 99th percentile of the null ($q_{0.99} = 1.16513$).

Together, these global tests indicate that future converters already exhibit detectable network-level reorganization at baseline (preclinical stage), and that additional reconfiguration accompanies conversion.

To facilitate interpretation of these whole-network findings, we provide complementary visual summaries of edge-wise effects and network structure. Specifically, Figure 2 depicts the estimated EBICglasso networks within each

group/timepoint (stable controls at T0, future converters at T0, and converters at T1), whereas Figure 3 summarizes the distribution of edge-wise effect sizes and BH-FDR significance for the baseline and longitudinal contrasts. The localization of edge-wise differences is further visualized using ΔW heatmaps (Figure 4) and network plots restricted to significant edges (Figure 5).

3.3. Edge-wise network differences at baseline (T0): stable controls vs future converters

Edge-wise inference using a bootstrap/permutation framework with BH-FDR correction identified 50 significant edges out of 190 at T0 ($q < 0.05$). The overall distribution of edge-wise effects is shown in Figure 3 (left), and the localization of effects is shown in Figure 4A; a complementary network visualization of significant edges is provided in Figure 5A. The top-ranked differential edges are reported in Table 2.

Among the strongest baseline differences ($\Delta = \text{converter} - \text{control}$), several edges reached the minimum attainable permutation resolution and are therefore reported as $p < 0.0005$ (e.g., for the top-ranked edges $q \approx 0.003$). These included increased coupling within semantic fluency (*fruits–tools*, $\Delta = +0.292$; $q = 0.0030$), marked reconfiguration among phonemic fluency letters (*m–r*, $\Delta = -0.283$; *p–m*, $\Delta = +0.251$; both $q = 0.0030$), altered coupling within verbal episodic memory (*FCSRT free immediate–total immediate*, $\Delta = -0.235$; $q = 0.0030$), and cross-domain differences involving processing speed (*ROCF time–digit symbol*, $\Delta = +0.211$; $q = 0.0030$) and working memory (*digit forward–digit backward*, $\Delta = -0.150$; $q = 0.0030$).

3.4. Within-converter longitudinal reconfiguration (paired): T1 – T0

Within converters, edge-wise testing of paired change identified 78 significant edges out of 190 after BH-FDR correction ($q < 0.05$), indicating widespread reconfiguration accompanying clinical conversion. The overall distribution of longitudinal edge-wise changes is shown in Figure 3 (right) and the localization of effects is shown in Figure 4B; a complementary network visualization of significant edges is provided in Figure 5B. The top-ranked changing edges are reported in Table 3.

The most prominent changes ($\Delta = T1 - T0$) again frequently reached $p < 0.0005$ (top-ranked set $q \approx 0.00176$). These were dominated by a strong reorganization of the phonemic fluency triad: $m-r$ increased ($\Delta = +0.485$; $q = 0.00176$), whereas $p-m$ ($\Delta = -0.354$; $q = 0.00176$) and $p-r$ ($\Delta = -0.329$; $q = 0.00176$) decreased. Robust changes were also observed within the ROCF block (*ROCF time-ROCF copy*, $\Delta = -0.346$; $q = 0.00176$; *ROCF copy-ROCF immediate*, $\Delta = +0.246$; $q = 0.00176$; *ROCF immediate-ROCF delayed*, $\Delta = -0.245$; $q = 0.00176$) and in semantic fluency (*fruits-tools*, $\Delta = -0.315$; $q = 0.00176$).

3.5. Modular localization of edge-wise effects

To summarize localization, significant edges were mapped onto a fixed community structure derived from Louvain community detection applied to the absolute-weight adjacency matrix of the stable-control T0 network, yielding the following four modules: (i) Module 1: animals; FCSRT free immediate; FCSRT total delayed; ROCF time. (ii) Module 2: MMSE; FCSRT total immediate; ROCF copy; ROCF immediate; digit span forward/backward; BNT spontaneous; phonemic fluency P and R. (iii) Module 3: clock drawing; fruits; phonemic fluency M. (iv) Module 4: digit symbol; FCSRT free delayed; ROCF delayed; tools.

At baseline, significant edges were predominantly between-module (34/50, 68%) rather than within-module (16/50, 32%). The most frequently implicated module pairs were 2–4 (n = 11), 2–2 (n = 10), and 2–3 (n = 7). Longitudinally (T1 – T0 within MCI converters), reconfiguration was again predominantly between-module (59/78, 75.6%) rather than within-module (19/78, 24.4%), with the most frequent module pair again 2–4 (n = 18), followed by 2–2 (n = 13), 1–2 (n = 12), and 2–3 (n = 11). Together, these summaries indicate that both baseline differences (preclinical stage) and conversion-related changes are driven mainly by inter-domain (between-module) alterations.

4. Discussion

In this study we examined whether the organization of a multivariate cognitive connectome differs before clinical conversion to MCI and across the conversion interval within the same individuals. Two complementary results support this idea. First, we observed significant whole-network differences between stable controls and future converters already at baseline, and significant whole-network reconfiguration from T0 to T1 within converters. Second, these global effects were accompanied by widespread edge-level differences at baseline (50/190 edges) and changes over time within converters (78/190 edges), which were not confined to a single domain but were predominantly between-module (inter-domain) rather than within-module. Together, the results suggest that conversion to MCI is preceded and accompanied by a measurable reorganization of the multivariate dependency structure among cognitive measures, beyond isolated test score declines. Therefore, the transition to MCI is not a topologically static process but involves a

subtle rebalancing of how cognitive functions cohere and interact across the entire system^{4,5,11}.

4.1. Preclinical network-level reorganization in future converters

A key finding is that the overall network structure at T0 differed between stable controls and individuals who would later convert to MCI (Figure 1). Because all converters were clinically cognitively normal at baseline, this supports the interpretation that subclinical changes in the coordination of cognitive systems can be detectable before overt diagnostic transition. Importantly, the baseline global effect was not driven by a single edge: the edge-wise analysis identified a distributed set of significant differences spanning memory, fluency, speed/visuoconstruction, and working memory. This pattern is consistent with the idea that early disease processes may alter the relationship between cognitive processes (i.e., how scores covary conditionally), not only their mean levels. This suggests that the cognitive connectome is a sensitive framework for identifying individuals on a preclinical trajectory toward MCI by capturing alterations in system-level coordination before diagnostic thresholds are met^{5,8,12}. In addition, other studies have examined the relationship between the connectome and cognition in patients with MCI. For example, Li et al. (2020) observed a strong association between executive function and altered topological efficiency in patients with amnesic MCI, suggesting, like our study, that quantified metrics of the connectome graph could serve as measurable biomarkers for assessing MCI.

4.2. Conversion-related reconfiguration within individuals (T1 – T0)

Within converters, we observed a significant global shift from T0 to T1 and a larger number of significant edge changes (78/190) compared with the baseline contrast.

This is in line with conversion representing not only quantitative decline but also a reorganization in how cognitive subsystems interact. These findings align with the perspective that clinically meaningful change in neurodegeneration involves not just quantitative decline, but a fundamental reorganization of the relational architecture through which cognitive subsystems interact^{4,5}. Notably, several of the strongest longitudinal changes involved tightly related task families (e.g., phonemic fluency triad; ROCF block), but the modular analyses indicate that the overall pattern is dominated by between-module changes. A plausible interpretation is that as impairment emerges, compensatory or failure-related processes manifest as altered cross-domain coupling (e.g., changes in the extent to which fluency performance depends on working memory, speed, or visuospatial organization). Thus, it is likely that the impact of neuropathological damage on effortful cognitive processing may lead to common variations in task performance across various cognitive functions and, consequently, to an exacerbated manifestation of de-differentiation in the cognitive network¹⁰.

4.3. Inter-domain effects and modular interpretation

Mapping significant edges to modules derived from the stable-control baseline network provides a higher-level view of where changes occur. In both contrasts, significant edges were more often between modules than within modules, suggesting that reconfiguration is primarily expressed as altered cross-domain integration rather than localized within-domain coupling. In practical terms, this means that conversion risk and conversion-related decline may be reflected in how memory, executive/fluency, visuospatial, and speed-related measures “hang together” conditionally, rather than in any single cognitive domain acting in

isolation. This result is consistent with other findings regarding the influence of significant changes in brain network functioning on the overall cognitive system, which could influence variations in task performance in a similar manner across all cognitive domains, leading to greater interconnectivity throughout the entire network¹⁰. Clinically meaningful change in neurodegenerative research involves not just domain-specific decline, but a fundamental reorganization of the architecture through which these domains interact. Our findings provide empirical evidence for this shift in relational organization during the transition to MCI^{4,5,6}.

That said, module composition was data-driven and included mixed-domain nodes (e.g., global cognition, memory, visuoconstruction, and attention measures co-occurring within a module). This is not a limitation per se (i.e., it may reflect the real multivariate structure of the battery in stable aging), but it does mean module labels should be interpreted cautiously. The clearest and most reproducible take-home from the modular results is therefore the between-module predominance, rather than a strong claim about any one module reflecting a pure cognitive domain.

4.4. Relation to conventional (univariate) cognitive differences

Table 1 confirms that future converters already show lower performance at baseline and decline from T0 to T1 across many tests. The network analyses extend these findings by showing that conversion is associated with a measurable whole-network shift and a distributed pattern of conditional association changes (Figures 3–5). This distinction matters clinically and conceptually: two individuals may have similar levels of impairment on a given test but differ in the pattern of inter-test dependencies, potentially reflecting different underlying mechanisms, compensatory strategies, or heterogeneous pathologies. By utilizing a network-

based approach, we addressed a key limitation of univariate methods: the inability to determine if the pattern of interdependence itself has changed. Our results demonstrate that even when scores remain within conventional diagnostic limits, the underlying conditional associations have already begun to reorganize^{4,5,7}.

Several aspects of the analytic design strengthen interpretability. Networks were estimated as regularized GGMs (EBICglasso), meaning edges reflect partial associations conditional on the remaining nodes rather than marginal correlations. Consequently, changes in an edge can be interpreted as changes in the unique statistical relationship between two cognitive measures, conditional on the rest of the battery. The study also combined (a) a global test (Frobenius distance with permutation) and (b) edge-wise inference with multiplicity control (BH-FDR), which helps avoid over-interpreting individual edges while still allowing localization of effects.

At the same time, edge weights should not be interpreted causally, and differences may reflect a mixture of true cognitive-system interactions, measurement characteristics of the tasks, and the effects of regularization. Moreover, permutation p-values depend on the number of permutations (with a minimum attainable p-value given the +1 correction), and the global null in Figure 1 was displayed via a smooth approximation for visualization. These choices do not invalidate inference but should be borne in mind when comparing magnitudes across studies that use different estimators or resampling schemes.

4.5. Limitations and future directions

This work has several limitations that suggest directions for follow-up. First, clinical diagnoses were reached by consensus and were not based on fixed psychometric

thresholds, which may introduce diagnostic heterogeneity and site/project effects. Second, the longitudinal analysis compares two timepoints; additional waves would enable modelling of trajectories and more granular dynamic reconfiguration. Third, although we adjusted cognitive nodes for demographic covariates and used pooled standardization, residual confounding and cohort effects cannot be entirely excluded. Fourth, network estimates can be sensitive to preprocessing and estimator choices; future work should examine robustness across alternative estimators, tuning parameters, and stability metrics, and evaluate reproducibility in independent cohorts. Finally, integrating biomarkers (e.g., amyloid/tau, MRI, vascular burden) could clarify whether specific network reconfiguration patterns are associated with particular underlying etiologies.

Despite these limitations, the results support the view that cognitive change in the run-up to MCI is not merely a collection of isolated score declines but involves a measurable reorganization of the multivariate cognitive system. If replicated, such network-level signatures could contribute to earlier risk stratification and to a mechanistic framing of preclinical cognitive change (e.g., altered cross-domain integration), complementing conventional neuropsychological profiling.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

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TABLE 1. Sample characteristics and cognitive performance at T0 and T1.

	STABLE CONTROLS (T0)	MCI CONVERTERS (T0)	MCI CONVERTERS (T1)	FDR- adjusted T0-T0	Effect size T0-T0	FDR- adjusted T0-T1	Effect size T0-T1
Age [mean (SD)]	74.14 (3.55)	76.36 (4.05)	79.28 (4.09)	<0.0001	0.610	<0.0001	3.275
Gender							
Male [n (%)]	243 (39.4%)	43 (37.1%)	43 (37.1%)	0.6391	0.017	-	-
Female [n (%)]	374 (60.6%)	73 (62.9%)	73 (62.9%)				
Education							
Illiterate [n (%)]	109 (17.7%)	20 (17.2%)	20 (17.2%)	0.0665	0.100	-	-
Primary Education [n (%)]	156 (25.3%)	43 (37.1%)	43 (37.1%)				
Secondary Education [n (%)]	168 (27.2%)	24 (20.7%)	24 (20.7%)				
Higher Education [n (%)]	184 (29.8%)	29 (25.0%)	29 (25.0%)				
MMSE [mean (SD)]	28.84 (1.26)	27.80 (1.90)	25.66 (3.16)	<0.0001	-0.751	<0.0001	-0.811
ROCF time [mean (SD)]	240.92 (114.82)	292.68 (138.24)	289.22 (170.97)	0.0003	-0.435	0.8463	0.018
ROCF copy [mean (SD)]	30.95 (6.12)	27.50 (8.24)	20.41 (12.49)	<0.0001	-0.529	<0.0001	-0.619
ROCF immediate [mean (SD)]	13.71 (6.16)	9.55 (5.34)	6.10 (5.51)	<0.0001	-0.688	<0.0001	-0.615
ROCF delayed [mean (SD)]	13.51 (6.26)	9.23 (5.36)	4.29 (5.56)	<0.0001	-0.698	<0.0001	-0.714
FCSRT free immediate [mean (SD)]	25.01 (5.84)	18.53 (5.66)	14.11 (6.32)	<0.0001	-1.113	<0.0001	-0.681
FCSRT total immediate [mean (SD)]	42.31 (4.68)	37.80 (6.38)	32.59 (8.20)	<0.0001	-0.902	<0.0001	-0.635
FCSRT free delayed [mean (SD)]	10.00 (2.34)	7.41 (2.63)	4.66 (3.18)	<0.0001	-1.085	<0.0001	-0.859
FCSRT total delayed [mean (SD)]	14.73 (1.49)	13.16 (2.19)	10.75 (3.22)	<0.0001	-0.967	<0.0001	-0.711
Phonemic fluency: P [mean (SD)]	14.04 (4.52)	12.87 (4.80)	11.81 (4.95)	0.0200	-0.255	0.0056	-0.265
Phonemic fluency: M [mean (SD)]	11.91 (4.25)	11.07 (4.95)	6.93 (5.31)	0.0938	-0.191	<0.0001	-0.603
Phonemic fluency: R [mean (SD)]	12.14 (4.40)	10.89 (4.39)	7.55 (5.58)	0.0070	-0.284	<0.0001	-0.524
Semantic fluency: animals [mean (SD)]	19.37 (4.92)	15.91 (4.35)	13.41 (4.37)	<0.0001	-0.714	<0.0001	-0.584
Semantic fluency: fruits [mean (SD)]	18.14 (4.06)	15.53 (4.26)	13.34 (4.21)	<0.0001	-0.638	<0.0001	-0.524
Semantic fluency: tools [mean (SD)]	13.76 (3.14)	11.60 (3.18)	7.38 (5.07)	<0.0001	-0.686	<0.0001	-0.746
Clock drawing [mean (SD)]	9.50 (0.94)	8.95 (1.46)	8.59 (1.88)	0.0003	-0.521	0.0291	-0.207
Digit forward [mean (SD)]	7.47 (1.88)	7.09 (1.66)	6.49 (1.62)	0.0370	-0.200	<0.0001	-0.435
Digit backward [mean (SD)]	4.75 (1.87)	4.20 (1.62)	3.71 (1.52)	0.0017	-0.300	0.0004	-0.347
BNT spontaneous [mean (SD)]	12.53 (2.24)	10.62 (3.25)	9.99 (3.52)	<0.0001	-0.787	0.0021	-0.297
Digit symbol [mean (SD)]	20.73 (7.50)	15.41 (6.05)	12.18 (6.03)	<0.0001	-0.728	<0.0001	-0.717

TABLE 2. Top differential edges at baseline (T0): cross-sectional analysis between stable controls vs future converters.

Edge	Δ (converter – control)	t	p	q (BH-FDR)
Fruits – Tools	0.292	20.218	<0.0005	0.0030
M – R	-0.283	-21.415	<0.0005	0.0030
P – M	0.251	17.511	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT free immediate – FCSRT total immediate	-0.235	-30.124	<0.0005	0.0030
ROCF time – Digit symbol	0.211	13.009	<0.0005	0.0030
MMSE – ROCF copy	0.166	11.534	<0.0005	0.0030
Digit forward – Digit backward	-0.150	-7.492	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT free delayed – FCSRT total delayed	0.142	11.470	<0.0005	0.0030
MMSE – FCSRT total immediate	0.136	13.511	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT total immediate – BNT spontaneous	0.130	12.986	<0.0005	0.0030
Animals – Fruits	0.110	6.451	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT total immediate – FCSRT total delayed	0.106	11.216	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT free immediate – FCSRT free delayed	0.082	11.496	<0.0005	0.0030
P – R	0.058	4.291	<0.0005	0.0030
M – Animals	0.054	6.738	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT total delayed – Clock drawing	0.046	6.482	<0.0005	0.0030
Digit forward – Digit symbol	0.045	5.472	<0.0005	0.0030
ROCF time – Animals	0.043	5.620	<0.0005	0.0030
FCSRT total delayed – Animals	-0.038	-6.245	<0.0005	0.0030
ROCF immediate – ROCF delayed	0.036	11.880	<0.0005	0.0030

TABLE 3. Top differential changing edges over time (T0-T1): longitudinal analysis within MCI converters.

Edge	$\Delta (T1 - T0)$	t	p	q (BH-FDR)
M – R	0.485	47.021	<0.0005	0.0018
P – M	-0.354	-29.219	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF time – ROCf copy	-0.346	-27.300	<0.0005	0.0018
P – R	-0.329	-34.505	<0.0005	0.0018
M – Tools	0.322	38.048	<0.0005	0.0018
Fruits – Tools	-0.315	-25.262	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF copy – ROCF immediate	0.246	26.857	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF immediate – ROCF delayed	-0.245	-41.950	<0.0005	0.0018
R – Tools	0.237	29.756	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF copy – ROCF delayed	-0.185	-30.122	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF copy – Digit symbol	0.134	12.625	<0.0005	0.0018
Animals - Fruits	-0.128	-7.760	<0.0005	0.0018
FCSRT free immediate – FCSRT free delayed	-0.121	-11.165	<0.0005	0.0018
MMSE – ROCF copy	-0.119	-10.082	<0.0005	0.0018
Digit forward – Digit backward	-0.117	-7.508	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF delayed – M	0.112	14.003	<0.0005	0.0018
M – Animals	-0.092	-9.899	<0.0005	0.0018
MMSE – FCSRT total immediate	-0.092	-9.753	<0.0005	0.0018
FCSRT total immediate – FCSRT total delayed	0.082	12.850	<0.0005	0.0018
ROCF copy – Clock drawing	0.072	6.571	<0.0005	0.0018

FIGURE 1. Whole-network cognitive connectome differences at baseline and during conversion.

Permutation-based whole-network contrasts using the Frobenius distance $D = \|W_1 - W_0\|_F$ between EBICglasso weight matrices. Left: baseline (T0) stable controls vs future converters (size-matched permutation, $D_{obs} = 1.0905$, one-sided $p = 0.0049975$; $q_{0.99} = 1.0607$). Right: within-converter longitudinal contrast (paired-swap permutation, $D_{obs} = 1.2420$, one-sided $p = 0.0019990$; $q_{0.99} = 1.1651$). The null distribution is displayed as a Normal approximation using the empirical null mean/SD from permutations; vertical lines denote D_{obs} (red), null mean (dashed), and the 95th/99th percentiles (dotted).

FIGURE 2. Descriptive EBICglasso cognitive networks across groups and time.

Heatmaps show estimated EBICglasso edge weights (regularized partial associations) for (A) stable controls at baseline (T_0 ; $n = 617$), (B) future converters at baseline (T_0 ; $n = 116$), and (C) converters at follow-up (T_1 ; $n = 116$). Node order is fixed across panels using the Louvain community structure of the stable-control T_0 network as a reference, and nodes are grouped within each module to keep subtests from the same instrument adjacent. A shared diverging color scale is used across panels to facilitate visual comparison of network structure between groups (stable vs future converters at T_0) and within converters over time (T_0 vs T_1).

FIGURE 3. Edge-wise network differences at baseline and longitudinal reconfiguration within converters.

Volcano-style summaries of edge-wise effects. Each point represents one of the 190 undirected edges of the 20-node cognitive network. The x-axis shows the mean edge-weight difference Δw (left: converter - control at T0; right: T1 - T0 within converters), and the y-axis shows $-\log_{10}(q_{FDR})$ from BH-FDR correction across edges. Red points indicate edges significant at $q_{FDR} < 0.05$; selected top-ranked edges are annotated.

FIGURE 4. ΔW heatmaps localize baseline network differences and conversion-related reconfiguration.

Heatmaps of mean edge-weight differences (ΔW) derived from edge-wise bootstrap/permutation framework. (A) Baseline case–control contrast at T0 (future converters – stable controls). (B) Within-converter paired contrast (T1 – T0). Cells display ΔW for all undirected edges (20 nodes; 190 edges). Black markers denote edges surviving BH-FDR correction ($q < 0.05$). Rows/columns are ordered by the Louvain community structure of the stable-control T0 network (reference) and, within each community, grouped by test family (e.g., ROCF and FCSRT subtests adjacent). A shared diverging color scale is used across panels to facilitate direct comparison of effect magnitudes.

FIGURE 5. Network plots of significant edge-wise differences at baseline and longitudinally.

Network visualizations of the 20-node cognitive connectome showing only edges significant at $q(FDR) < 0.05$. (A) Baseline case–control contrast (future converters – stable controls at T0). (B) Longitudinal within-converter contrast (T1 – T0). Edge width is proportional to the absolute mean difference ($|\Delta|$), and edge color indicates the sign of the difference (red = positive, blue = negative). Nodes are colored by their module membership derived from the stable-control T0 network. The layout is fixed across panels to facilitate direct visual comparison.